

Average Happiness Index (AHI) as a Quality Indicator of Collaborative Practices and Activities (CPAs) Between Makati LGU and its Cooperatives: Towards A Stronger and More Inclusive Cooperative Governance

Leonardo N. Pasquito

University of Makati, Philippines

leonardo.pasquito@umak.edu.ph

Article Details:

Received: 15 February 2026

Revised: 20 February 2026

Accepted: 23 February 2026

Published: 28 February 2026

Corresponding Email:

leonardo.pasquito@umak.edu.ph

Recommended Citation:

Pasquito, L. N. (2026). Average Happiness Index (AHI) as a Quality Indicator of Collaborative Practices and Activities (CPAs) Between Makati LGU and its Cooperatives: Towards A Stronger and More Inclusive Cooperative Governance. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1 (2), 107-120.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18812396>

Index Terms:

average happiness index, collaborative practices, cooperatives, federation, local government unit, makati cooperatives, cooperative governance

Abstract. According to the 2025 World Happiness Report, Philippines ranks as the 57th happiest country, with Finland as the happiest and Afghanistan as the least happy, while ranking 4th in Southeast Asia. While happiness index serves as essential metric for assessing a country's mental and emotional well-being, it can be used as a valuable quality indicator of collaborative Projects, Programs, and Activities (PPAs) between organizations and its local government. This research aimed to evaluate the extent and quality of collaborative practices of the LGU Makati as seen under the lens of affiliates of the Federation of Makati Cooperatives (FEMACO). The study employed surveys, key informant interviews, and group discussions between cooperative leaders and local government officials. A t-test was conducted to determine significant difference in happiness indices between respondents: the Board of Directors and LGU Officials. Findings revealed that FEMACO affiliates displayed varying happiness indices in relation to the extent of collaborative practices in terms of compliance to laws and circulars, recognition programs, technical support, capacity building, promotional activities, and partnership and linkages. The study shed light on the perceptions, inclusiveness, and collaborative values essential for promotion and growth of cooperatives as instruments of social justice, equity and economic development. Finally, the study highlights internal and external challenges experienced by affiliates on PPAs collaboration. Ultimately, the study recommends not only expanding collaboration with the LGU but also forging partnerships with Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and community groups to create inclusive and empowered cooperatives essential in realizing the SDG of 2030.

Introduction

What makes Bhutan so happy and why is it considered one of the happiest countries in the world? The term 'Gross National Happiness' (GNH) was coined by Bhutan's 4th King, Jigme Singye Wangchuck, in the late 1970s, who asserted, that 'Gross National Happiness is more important than Gross Domestic Product.' The GNH is intended to provides a comprehensive approach toward measuring progress, prioritizing overall well-being and happiness over purely economic pursuits (OECD, 2024). Bhutan focus on developing a unique Gross National Happiness (GNH) model, a model that is centered around creating a balanced and sustainable development that takes into account various aspects of happiness, such as psychological well-being, health, education, living standards, good governance, and ecological diversity. Bhutanese Gross National Happiness Index was formed in 1972 and this gave an idea to the World Happiness Index. This unwavering focus on the overall well-being of its citizens has proven immensely successful and stands in stark contrast to other nations that prioritize economic indicators above well-being. Consequently, Bhutan has emerged as a leader in happiness policy and has

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-0507-2446>

© 2026 The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This article is subject to the journal's Corrections, Retractions, and Article Updates Policy, available at: <https://tinyurl.com/ysnr3356>

replaced the traditional GDP-based view of the economy. To understand Gross National Happiness (GNH) Model, cooperative leaders in particular should ask these questions: *What percentage of your cooperative members exhibit signs of contentment, as indicated by their smiles? How genuinely do they find enjoyment in their lives as members? What is the overall well-being of your membership in terms of their health? To what extent do they suffer from psychological challenges like stress, anxiety, or depression? How does your cooperative fare regarding mortality or illness rates within the membership? If these aspects were taken into account, what would be your cooperative's position in the Cooperative Sector in the context of the Average Happiness Index (AHI)?*

As of 2023, according to Hunter (2023), for the sixth year in a row, Finland is the world's happiest country, according to World Happiness Report rankings based largely on life evaluations from the Gallup World Poll. The Nordic country and its neighbors Denmark, Iceland, Sweden and Norway all score very well on the measures the report uses to explain its findings: healthy life expectancy, GDP per capita, social support, low corruption, generosity in a community where people look after each other and freedom to make key life decisions. However, Bhutan, despite being ranked 95th in the 2021 World Happiness Report, has gained global recognition for its innovative Gross National Happiness (GNH) Model. While Finland holds the top spot in happiness rankings, Bhutan is being sought after as a source of inspiration for effective policies that enhance citizens' well-being and happiness. Bhutan's distinction as "the Happiest Country in the World," as acknowledged by BBC News series "The World's Happiest Countries," can be attributed to its distinctive GNH index, which is used to gauge the well-being of its population. The GNH index in Bhutan focuses on four critical dimensions: good governance, sustainable socio-economic development, cultural preservation, and environmental conservation, influencing decisions for the country's well-being. Bhutan stands out by prioritizing a healthy and fulfilling lifestyle for its citizens, implementing policies like free healthcare, education, and environmental preservation. By replacing the GDP model with the Gross National Happiness (GNH) score, Bhutan has become the happiest country in the world. Bhutan's success serves as a global example that happiness should not be solely linked to economic gains. Locally, the GNH Model can be applied to evaluate the effectiveness of Project, Programs, and Activities within LGUs in promoting cooperatives in their jurisdictions.

Joint Memorandum Circular series of 2019-01 (JMC 2019-01), entered by and between Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) and the Cooperative Development Authority (CDA), outlines the roles of LGUs in promoting, organizing, and developing cooperatives. These roles include formulating local cooperative development plans, offering technical guidance and financial assistance, supporting cooperative development, appointing local cooperative officers, establishing partnerships with the CDA, assisting with registration and reports, providing cooperative training, implementing localized cooperative promotion programs, and sharing information with the CDA. The study in question focuses on the collaborative practices and activities of the LGU in Makati, which are based on these roles defined in JMC 2019-01.

As an LGU, the City of Makati was originally known as San Pedro de Makati, established in 1670 as a *visita* of Sta. Ana de Sapa under the Franciscans supervision. It was integrated into the province of Rizal in 1901, and on February 28, 1914, it was formally adopted the shorter name Makati through the passage of Act 2390. Even during the 1970s, Makati was already a prominent financial and commercial center. Much that it boomed into its present status when the status of a city was granted to it in 1995 with the enactment of RA 7854 during the tenure of former Mayor Jejomar C. Binay. Presently, the City of Makati is recognized as a highly urbanized, first-class city within the NCR, renowned as the country's primary financial center, with highest concentration of both multinational and local corporations. Makati continues to be one of the most financially prosperous both in terms of revenue derived from local sources and per capita income. In fact, on Business and Economic Development Sector, Makati ranks second, next to Quezon City (P433.4 billion), as the richest local government in the Philippines in 2022, with assets worth P239.48 billion, according to the Commission on Audit (Cruz, 2023). Business-wise, as of 2023, the City of Makati has 86,370 active business establishment, 44 PEZA registered and operating IT buildings, has 166 active cooperatives excluding cooperatives from 10 EMBO barangays. These cooperatives are composed of 4 billionaire coops, more than 70 large and medium coops, more than 80 small and micro coops, one union and one federation. (See Table 1).

Business Establishment	Number
Business Establishment (per activity)	86,370
PEZA Registered IT Buildings (Operating)	44
Active Cooperatives*	166
Community Savers Centers	38
Bank and Other Finance Related Institutions	4,798

Sources: Business Permits Office (BPO); International Relations Department (IRD); Makati Cooperative Development Office (MCDO); Philippine Economic Zone Authority (PEZA);
 Table 1. Makati City Basic Facts and Figures 2023 on Economic Development

Today, the Makati City through Mayor Mar-Len Abigail Binay has led the implementation of key programs that aims at expanding access to digital technology all over the city. Recently, Makati City was chosen as sole city in PH, Asia Pacific Region as finalist in World Smart City Awards 2023 with 411 entries from 63 countries. According to Garcia, 2023, Makati City local government was chosen as one of the six finalists in the prestigious World Smart City Awards 2023 in Barcelona, Spain, making it the only city in the country and the whole Asia Pacific Region to be included in the feat.

The Local Government of Makati has two secondary cooperatives, the Federation of Makati Cooperatives (FEMACO) and the Union of Primary Cooperative in Makati (UPCM). The FEMACO was formerly named as Federation of Makati Credit Cooperatives (FEMACCO) began its operation last August 28, 2011 with eight cooperative members. It was the first and the only federation then in the City of Makati. Its main business of member cooperatives was credit and loan business. However, with the membership of other cooperatives whose line of business is not credit but logistics and service, FEMACO changed its name from FEMACCO to FEMACO instead. Over its 12 years of existence, it doubles its membership to 16 cooperatives and through the years it gradually operated as a multipurpose secondary cooperative until today. Through its operations it had been an active participant of the cooperative movement in Makati City. Today, there are two secondary cooperatives in the city, the FEMACO and the Union of Primary Cooperatives in Makati (UPCM). At present, FEMACO is a micro secondary cooperative with an asset of more or less 961,000. The Federation had been a recipient this 2023 of the Koop Bida Awards Season 12 held at St. Giles Makati Hotel last October 12, 2023, as Best Partner Cooperative and Best Performing Cooperative in Terms of Corporate Social Responsibility. Table 2 outlines the profile of member-cooperatives of the Federation.

Member-Cooperatives	Type	Main Business	Size
MAKSAVE MPC	Multipurpose	Lending	Medium
PEN-COOP	Multipurpose	Lending	Medium
UMEMPC	Multipurpose	Lending	Medium
Barangay Rizal Cooperative	Multipurpose	Lending	Small
MACRECCO	Credit	Lending	Small
MAK-ED MPC	Multipurpose	Lending	Small
Palanan MPC	Multipurpose	Lending	Small
People Support Labor Service Cooperative	Credit	Lending	Small
PHILHSMET MPC	Multipurpose	Lending	Small
SAMAVEA MPC	Multipurpose	Lending	Small
TSPI Cooperative	Multipurpose	Lending and Savings	Small

Legend: MAKSAVE MPC (Makati Savings Multipurpose Cooperative); PEN-COOP (Peninsula Hotel Employees Multipurpose Cooperative); UMEMPC (University of Makati Employees Multipurpose Cooperative); MACRECCO (Makati City Retirees Employees Credit Cooperative); MAK-ED MPC (Makati Educators Multipurpose Cooperative); PHILHSMET Coop (Philippine Humanitarian Support Mission to East Timor Multi-Purpose Cooperative); SAMAVEA MPC (Sacramento Market Vendors Association Multi-Purpose Cooperative); TSPI Coop (Tulay sa Pag-unlad, Inc Cooperative)

Table 2. Profile of Member-Cooperatives of the Federation of Makati Cooperatives (FEMACO)

This study therefore identified the extent of the collaborative practices and activities of the LGU of Makati to its Cooperatives. It also evaluates the quality of collaborative practices and activities in terms of average happiness index (AHI) through the lens of the Federation of Makati Cooperatives. Moreover, it determines if there a significant difference of the average happiness index (AHI) between two groups of respondents (BOD and GM). This study is anchored on the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the Happiness Indexes of the two groups of respondents. And finally, this study collated recommendations from respondents on how to create a stronger and more inclusive cooperative governance in the City.

In the Philippines, economic progress of businesses is usually measured in terms of Gross National Product (GNP) or by its Gross Domestic Product (GDP). GDP is the value of the finished domestic goods and services produced within a nation's borders while GNP is the value of all finished goods and services produced by a country's citizens, both domestically and abroad. Changes in GDP is used by the White House and US Congress to prepare the Federal budget, by the Federal Reserve to formulate monetary policy, and by Wall Street as an indicator of economic activity. GDP is also used by both the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank (WB) to guide financial policies and determine which projects should be funded around the world. However, economists have warned that GDP as an indicator of indicator of the success of economic and fiscal policies is inaccurate and dangerous because it only measures monetary transactions related to the production of goods and services. Such is an incomplete picture of the system within which the human economy operates. Of particular concern is that GDP measurement encourages the depletion of natural resources faster and that current economic activity is degrading ecosystems. Another concern about GDP as a measure of progress is the 'threshold effect.'

Beyond a certain threshold, further increases in material well-being have the negative side effects of lowering community cohesion, healthy relationships, knowledge, wisdom, a sense of purpose, connection with nature, and other dimensions of human happiness.

Gross National Happiness (GNH) is frequently mentioned as an alternative measure of economic and moral progress or alternative to gross domestic product. It was originally suggested by the King of Bhutan in the early 1980s as a more appropriate measure for his small kingdom than GDP. It was not an actual index, but a principle for guiding Bhutanese development in a fashion consistent with the country's culture and spiritual values rather than by focusing on increasing economic activity. Rather than focusing strictly on quantitative economic measures, gross national happiness takes into account an evolving mix of quality-of-life factors. The term "Gross National Happiness" as conceptualized by the 4th King of Bhutan, Jigme Singye Wangchuck, in 1972 was declared as, "more important than Gross Domestic Product." The concept implies that sustainable development should take a holistic approach towards notions of progress and give equal importance to non-economic aspects of wellbeing. (Arns & Lima, 2020).

GNH is distinguishable from GDP by valuing collective happiness as the goal of governance, by emphasizing harmony with nature and traditional values as expressed in the domains of happiness and 4 pillars of GNH. According to the Bhutanese government, the four pillars of GNH are sustainable and equitable socio-economic development; environmental conservation; preservation and promotion of culture; and good governance. The nine domains of GNH are psychological well-being, health, time use, education, cultural diversity and resilience, good governance, community vitality, ecological diversity and resilience, and living standards. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is a measure of economic development and growth, while Gross National Happiness (GNH) is a measurement of happiness and wellbeing. In effect, GNH measures how people feel about their lives. Using happiness as its measure of "development", GNH can be used to compare different countries with respect to their economic performance. A country's GNH can be measured by measuring happiness at its natural state, which is not restricted to money or income but includes other living standards such as food security, education, healthcare, housing conditions and more. Happiness is a difficult concept to measure. (Russo, 2022).

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-method approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative research designs. In the quantitative phase, the researcher employed survey questionnaires to gather data from a predetermined group of participants. This approach aimed to gather insights into various subjects of interest and facilitate the generalization of findings from the sample group to the larger population. The survey was administered both online and offline. To ensure the quality of the survey, Subject Matter Experts (SMEs) validated the questionnaire. Additionally, a trial survey was conducted to collect feedback and assess the time and motion required to complete the questionnaire. For the online survey component, the researcher utilized Google Forms, which were distributed through digital platforms including survey applications, social media networks, emails, and messaging services. This paper used a modified version of the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) questionnaire. It is a 20-item questionnaire, using a five-point Likert scale (1 = very slightly or not at all, 5 = extremely) to assess the relation between personality traits and positive or negative affects at "this moment, today, the past few days, the past week, the past few weeks, the past year, and in general". The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS scale) is a self-assessment questionnaire for measuring your emotions and feelings. The PANAS scale is broken into two sections to measure both your positive affect and negative affect. Positive affect refers to your tendency to experience positive emotions, and the higher your positive affect the more prevalent these emotions are, while the Negative affect is the opposite and refers to the level of negative emotions one is experiencing.

In the qualitative methodology, the researcher employed various techniques including Key Informant Interviews or open-ended interviews, focus group discussions. Open-ended interviews were used to delve deeply into participants' viewpoints, as they were encouraged to offer detailed and unrestricted responses through open-ended questions. Similarly, Focus Group Discussions (FGD) involved assembling a small group of individuals guided by a moderator to explore a specific topic to generate comprehensive qualitative data, capture group dynamics, uncover shared beliefs and societal norms, and reveal underlying motivations and attitudes. The Focus Group Discussions was also utilized to validate certain aspects that were not clearly addressed by both the Survey and Key Informant Interviews. In this study, the member-cooperatives only of the Federation of Makati Cooperative were the unit of the study. Discussions were held to find out any similarities and diversity related to Happiness Index of the respondents.

In identifying the significant relationships of the perception of different groups of respondents, the researcher utilized t-tests, to find out if survey or results are significant in order to help the researcher to reject the null hypothesis or accept the alternative hypothesis.

Results and Analysis

In this study, there were 24 respondents who participated in the survey, 8 were General Managers and 16 were Board of Directors (See Table 3). Data shows that eight General Managers and 16 Board of Directors participated in the study. The UMEMPC (16.67%) and MACRECCO (16.67%) have the highest number of participants of four respondents each while PHILSMET (4.17%) has the least with only one respondent

Member-Cooperative	GM	BOD	Total	%
MACRECCO	0	4	4	16.67
MAK-ED MPC	1	1	2	8.33
MAKSAVE MPC	1	2	3	12.5
Palanan Multipurpose Cooperative	1	1	2	8.33
PEN-COOP	1	1	2	8.33
People Support Labor Service Cooperative	1	1	2	8.33
PHILSMET	1	0	1	4.17
SAMAVEA MPC	1	1	2	8.33
TSPI Cooperative	1	1	2	8.33
UMEMPC	1	3	4	16.67
Barangay Rizal Cooperative	0	0	0	0.00
TOTAL	8	16	24	100.00

Legend: MAKSAVE MPC (Makati Savings Multipurpose Cooperative); PEN-COOP (Peninsula Hotel Employees Multipurpose Cooperative); UMEMPC (University of Makati Employees Multipurpose Cooperative); MACRECCO (Makati City Retirees Employees Credit Cooperative); MAK-ED MPC (Makati Educators Multipurpose Cooperative); PHILSMET Coop (Philippine Humanitarian Support Mission to East Timor Multi-Purpose Cooperative); SAMAVEA MPC (Sacramento Market Vendors Association Multi-Purpose Cooperative); TSPI Coop (Tulay sa Pag-unlad, Inc Cooperative)

Table 3. Respondents of the Study

The Focus Group Discussion (FGD) identified major common themes for the major CPAs. On compliance with laws and circulars, respondents suggested establishing institutional structures, such as the MCDO and CDO, and ensuring cooperatives benefit from tax incentives and regulatory support. On technical assistance centers on providing accessible guidance through compliance forums, prompt inquiries, and cooperative cliniquing to strengthen operations. Capacity building emphasizes structured training programs, qualified trainers, and business continuity initiatives to enhance competencies and resilience. Promotional activities suggested to increase cooperative visibility and engagement through organized programs and public events. Lastly, partnerships and linkages highlight collaboration with academic institutions, federations, and government agencies to expand resources, expertise, and opportunities for cooperative development (See Table 4).

Discussion Topic	Common Themes from Respondents
<i>A. Compliance to Laws and Circulars</i>	▪ Establishment of MCDO; Appointment of CDO; Tax Exemptions and Incentives
<i>B. Technical Assistance</i>	▪ Compliance Forum; Open and Swift Inquiries; Cooperative Cliniquing
<i>C. Capacity Building</i>	▪ MCDO as Cooperative Training Provider (CTPro); Seasoned Pool of Trainers; Business Continuity Program
<i>D. Promotional Activities</i>	▪ Koop Kapatid Program; Ginoo at Ginang Kooperatiba; Koop Quiz Bee; Koop Caravan Program
<i>E. Partnership and Linkages</i>	▪ Partnership with CDCM; Partnership with UPCM; Partnership with FEMACO; and Partnership with other Government Agencies (DTI, DA, and DOLE)

Table 4. Common Themes of Collaborative Practices and Activities from Key Informant

Figure 1 illustrates LGU Makati's compliance to Cooperative Law and Circulars. The majority of the respondents expressed extreme happiness (4.67) with the establishment of the Makati Cooperative Development Office (MCDO) to oversee cooperative initiatives within the City. Conversely, respondents exhibited happiness (4.00) with LGU Makati's provision of cooperative tax exemptions and incentives for its business activities among its members. This is in consonance with Articles 60 and 61 of the Philippine Cooperative Code of 2008 which provide tax exemptions of

cooperatives in all its transactions with members, as a recognition that cooperatives are partners of the Government in community-building, and consequently, in nation-building. Likewise, respondents displayed happiness (3.89) with LGU Makati's support for the compliance programs, projects, and activities (PPAs) initiated by the MCDO in the City.

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Extremely happy; 3.51–4.50 – Happy; 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Happy; 1.51–2.50 – Quite a bit happy; 1.00–1.50 – Not at all happy

Figure 1. Respondents' Average Happiness Index (AHI) on LGU's Compliance to Cooperative Laws and Circulars.

Figure 2 reveals that respondents express happiness (4.11) with the LGU of Makati, facilitated by the MCDO, for its implementation of various recognition programs and activities. Moreover, respondents demonstrate happiness (4.11) with the LGU's practice of acknowledging the top-performing cooperatives through the Koop Bida Awards. In addition, respondents display a notable degree of happiness (3.78) regarding the fairness and equity of the criteria employed for recognizing the best-performing cooperatives within the City.

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Extremely happy; 3.51–4.50 – Happy; 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Happy; 1.51–2.50 – Quite a bit happy; 1.00–1.50 – Not at all happy

Figure 2. Average Happiness Index (AHI) on LGU's Recognition of Cooperatives

Figure 3 provides data showing that respondents express a significant degree of happiness (3.89) with the fact that LGU Makati, through the MCDO, offers technical support to individual cooperatives via its Compliance Forum. Likewise, respondents demonstrate happiness (3.56) with LGU Makati, facilitated by the MCDO, ensuring swift responses to cooperative inquiries via email, phone calls, and various communication channels. Additionally, respondents indicate that they are reasonably happy (3.56) with the assistance provided by LGU Makati, through the MCDO, in generating reports, organizing programs and events, and addressing basic troubleshooting needs related to their mandated reports.

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Extremely happy; 3.51–4.50 – Happy; 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Happy; 1.51–2.50 – Quite a bit happy; 1.00–1.50 – Not at all happy

Figure 3. Average Happiness Index (AHI) on LGU's Technical Assistance to Cooperatives

Figure 4 presents that respondents are happy (4.11) with the LGU of Makati, guided by the MCDO, functioning as the Cooperative Training Provider (CTPro) for cooperatives within the City of Makati. On the other hand, respondents are moderately happy (3.44) that the LGU, through the MCDO, cultivates a group of cooperative trainers who are actively engaged in delivering both mandated and non-mandated training sessions to members. Moreover, they also express happiness (3.55) that the LGU, under the MCDO's auspices, aids cooperatives in formulating their Cooperative Business Continuity Program to enhance their preparedness for emergencies, disasters, and calamities.

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Extremely happy; 3.51–4.50 – Happy; 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Happy; 1.51–2.50 – Quite a bit happy; 1.00–1.50 – Not at all happy

Figure 4. Average Happiness Index (AHI) on LGU's Capacity Building

Figure 5 provides data indicating that respondents exhibit happiness (3.89) with LGU Makati's use of the *Koop Kapatid* Program as a means of promoting cooperativism in Makati City. They also express happiness (3.56) with the *Ginoo at Ginang Kooperatiba* program and to the *Koop Quiz Bee Activity* (3.67) as effective tools for promoting cooperativism in the City of Makati. On the other hand, respondents demonstrate a moderate degree of happiness (3.33) with the *Koop Caravan* Program as an instrument for advancing cooperativism at the barangay level.

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Extremely happy; 3.51–4.50 – Happy; 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Happy; 1.51–2.50 – Quite a bit happy; 1.00–1.50 – Not at all happy

Figure 5. Average Happiness Index (AHI) on LGU's Promotional Activities

Figure 6 portrays that respondents express a moderate degree of happiness (3.33) regarding the collaboration between MCDO and the Cooperative Development Council of Makati (CDCM) in coordinating cooperative programs and shaping cooperative policies in the City of Makati. They also demonstrate a moderate level of happiness (3.00) for the partnership between MCDO and the Union of Primary Cooperatives in Makati (UPCM) when it comes to executing capacity-building initiatives, particularly through Mandated Trainings.

On the other hand, respondents also display moderate happiness (2.89) with the partnership between MCDO and the Federation of Makati Cooperatives (FEMACO) when it comes to exploring new business opportunities and improving the financial programs and activities for its member-cooperatives. However, respondents express happiness (3.56) with MCDO's establishment of connections between cooperatives and various government agencies, such as DTI, DA, and DOLE, which fosters stronger partnerships and networking opportunities.

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Extremely happy; 3.51–4.50 – Happy; 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Happy; 1.51–2.50 – Quite a bit happy; 1.00–1.50 – Not at all happy

Figure 6. Average Happiness Index (AHI) on LGU's Partnership and Linkages.

Generally, Table 5 illustrates the Average Happiness Index (AHI) reflecting Collaborative Practices in the Local Government Unit (LGU). Concerning compliance with Cooperative Laws and Circulars from the Cooperative Development Authority (CDA), survey participants express contentment (scoring 4.26) with the establishment of the Municipal Cooperative Development Office (MCDO), the appointment of a regular Cooperative Development Officer (CDO), and LGU's support for various programs, projects, and activities (PPAs) aimed at promoting the cooperative movement within the city.

When it comes to recognizing outstanding cooperatives, respondents also express satisfaction (rating 4.00) with LGU Makati. This is facilitated by MCDO, which implements various recognition programs and activities, such as the Koop Bida Awards, and employs fair and equitable criteria.

Regarding Technical Assistance, respondents are pleased (scoring 3.67) with the technical support provided to individual cooperatives. This support is extended through the Compliance Forum, timely responses to cooperative inquiries, and assistance with generating reports, event organization, and addressing troubleshooting needs related to mandated reports.

In the context of Capacity Building (CB), respondents show contentment (scoring 3.70) with MCDO serving as the Cooperative Training Provider (CTPro), nurturing a group of cooperative trainers actively engaged in delivering both mandated and non-mandated trainings. They also appreciate MCDO's assistance in helping cooperatives formulate their Cooperative Business Continuity Program to enhance their readiness for emergencies, disasters, and calamities.

Similarly, in terms of Promotional Activities, respondents are pleased (scoring 3.61) with LGU Makati's promotional initiatives. These include programs like *Koop Kapatid*, *Ginoo at Ginang Kooperatiba*, *Koop Quiz Bee*, and the *Koop Caravan*, which promote cooperativism in Makati City and at the barangay level.

Moreover, in the realm of Partnership and Linkages (P&L), respondents express moderate satisfaction (scoring 3.19) with the collaboration between MCDO and the Cooperative Development Council of Makati (CDCM). This collaboration involves coordinating cooperative programs, shaping policies, working with the Union of Primary Cooperatives in Makati (UPCM) to deliver capacity-building initiatives, collaborating with the Federation of Makati Cooperatives (FEMACO) to explore business opportunities and enhance financial programs, and MCDO's efforts to establish connections with government agencies such as DTI, DA, and DOLE.

Collaborative Practices	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>Compliance to Laws and Circulars</i>	4.26	0.50	<i>Happy</i>
<i>Recognition Program</i>	4.00	0.33	<i>Happy</i>
<i>Technical Support</i>	3.67	0.60	<i>Happy</i>
<i>Capacity Building</i>	3.70	0.33	<i>Happy</i>
<i>Promotional Activities</i>	3.61	0.60	<i>Happy</i>
<i>Partnership and Linkages</i>	3.28	0.70	<i>Moderately Happy</i>
Average	3.74	0.51	Happy

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Extremely happy; 3.51–4.50 – Happy; 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Happy; 1.51–2.50 – Quite a bit happy; 1.00–1.50 – Not at all happy

Table 5. Average Happiness Index (AHI) of Respondents on Different Collaborative Practices

Data in Table 6 shows the Collaborative Practices and Activities in the LGU of Makati for the two groups of respondents, the Board of Directors (BOD) and General Managers (GM), show that in terms of Compliance to Laws and Circulars, both groups are "Happy" with a mean of 4.267 and 4.250, respectively, and relatively low standard deviations of 0.306 and 0.433, indicating minimal variation within the groups. Similarly, in the Recognition Programs and Technical Support practices, both groups also express "Happiness", with slight differences in scores and standard deviations. The same pattern of "Happy" responses continues for Capacity Building and Promotional Activities. However, in Partnership and Linkages, while BOD remains "Happy" with a score of 3.563 and a standard deviation of 0.239, the GM group is "Moderately Happy" with a score of 3.000 and a standard deviation of 0.432, suggesting a notable difference in their happiness or satisfaction levels in these collaborative activities. In sum, both groups are "Happy" with slight differences in their mean scores and standard deviations. It is noteworthy to pay attention to the specific areas where the groups exhibit varied levels of satisfaction, like Partnership and Linkages.

Collaborative Practices	Mean (BOD)	SD	VI	Mean (GM)	SD	VI
<i>Compliance to Laws and Circulars</i>	4.267	0.306	H	4.250	0.433	H
<i>Recognition Programs</i>	4.070	0.115	H	4.000	0.346	H
<i>Technical Support</i>	3.750	0.000	H	3.600	0.346	H
<i>Capacity Building</i>	3.667	0.289	H	3.733	0.416	H
<i>Promotional Activities</i>	3.813	0.239	H	3.450	0.252	H
<i>Partnership and Linkages</i>	3.563	0.239	H	3.000	0.432	MH
Grand Average	3.855	0.198	Happy	3.672	0.371	Happy

Legend: 4.51–5.00 – Extremely happy; 3.51–4.50 – Happy; 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Happy; 1.51–2.50 – Quite a bit happy; 1.00–1.50 – Not at all happy; SD- Standard Deviation; VI- Verbal Interpretation; BOD- Board of Directors; GM- General Manager; H-Happy; MH-Moderately Happy

Table 6. Average Happiness Index (AHI) Difference between BOD and GM

Table 7 shows ranking of Affiliates or Member-Cooperatives of the Federation of Makati Cooperatives (FEMACO) in terms of Average Happiness Index (AHI). Data illustrates the happiness levels of various member cooperatives of the Federation of Makati Cooperatives (FEMACO). TSPI Cooperative emerges as the happiest, with an impressive Average Happiness Index of 4.20, closely followed by MAKSAVE MPC, which secured the second spot with an Average Happiness Index of 3.92. UMEMPC ranks third, reporting an Average Happiness Index of 3.70, while PEN-COOP held the fourth position, with an Average Happiness Index of 3.65. MAK-ED MPC took the fifth spot, garnering an Average Happiness Index of 3.54. The remaining member-cooperatives occupy positions six through ten. Notably, Cooperative I and Cooperative J exhibited moderate happiness, with Cooperative J having the lowest Average Happiness Index at 3.22.

Member-Cooperative	Comp	Recog	Tech	Capac	Promo	Partner	AHI	VI	Rank
TSPI Cooperative	4.33	4.67	4.67	4.00	4.25	3.25	4.20	<i>H</i>	1
MAKSAVE MPC	4.33	4.33	4.00	3.835	3.50	3.50	3.92	<i>H</i>	2
UMEMPC	4.33	3.78	3.44	3.67	4.00	3.00	3.70	<i>H</i>	3
PEN-COOP	4.33	4.33	3.33	3.67	3.25	3.00	3.65	<i>H</i>	4
MAK-ED MPC	4.00	3.67	3.67	3.67	2.75	3.50	3.54	<i>H</i>	5
<i>Cooperative F</i>	4.33	4.00	4.00	4.00	3.25	3.25	3.81	<i>H</i>	6
<i>Cooperative G</i>	4.33	4.33	3.33	3.67	3.25	3.00	3.65	<i>H</i>	7
<i>Cooperative H</i>	4.00	3.67	3.67	3.67	2.75	3.50	3.54	<i>H</i>	8
<i>Cooperative I</i>	4.00	3.33	3.00	3.33	3.25	3.00	3.32	<i>MH</i>	9
<i>Cooperative J</i>	4.33	3.33	2.33	3.33	3.75	2.25	3.22	<i>MH</i>	10

Legend: TSPI Coop (Tulay sa Pag-unlad, Inc Cooperative); MAKSAVE MPC (Makati Savings Multipurpose Cooperative); UMEMPC (University of Makati Employees Multipurpose Cooperative); PEN-COOP (Peninsula Hotel Employees Multipurpose Cooperative); MAK-ED MPC (Makati Educators Multipurpose Cooperative); Range: 4.51–5.00 – Extremely happy; 3.51–4.50 – Happy; 2.51–3.50 – Moderately Happy; 1.51–2.50 – Quite a bit happy; 1.00–1.50 – Not at all happy; AHI-Average Happiness Index; VI- Verbal Interpretation; H-Happy; MH-Moderately Happy.

Table 7. AHI of Member-Cooperatives of FEMACO to the CPAs of LGU Makati.

Based on t-test analysis, On Compliance to Laws and Circulars, the P-value is 0.960, which is relatively high, indicating that there is not strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis for this category. The t-value is 0.055, indicating a small difference. On Recognition Program, the P-value is 0.768, again a relatively high value, suggesting that there is not strong evidence of a significant difference for this aspect. The t-value is 0.316. On Technical Support, the P-value is 0.495, still relatively high, which is moderately high, indicating no strong evidence of a significant difference. The t-value is 0.750. On Capacity Building, the P-value is 0.831, indicating weak evidence against the null hypothesis. The t-value is 0.228. However, on Promotional Activities, the P-value is 0.082, which is lower than the conventional significance level of 0.05 suggesting there may be some evidence to reject the null hypothesis for this aspect. The t-value is 2.088, indicating a relatively larger difference for this category. On the same manner, on Partnership and Linkages, the P-value is 0.063, also relatively low, indicating some evidence of a significant difference for this aspect. The t-value is 2.278, indicating a relatively larger difference for this category as well. In general, P-values below 0.05 are often considered statistically significant, meaning that there may be a significant difference or effect. P-values above 0.05 suggest that there is not enough evidence to conclude a significant difference. The t-statistic helps quantify the size and direction of any observed differences. In summary, Promotional Activities and Partnership and Linkages have statistically significant differences compared to the other categories, as indicated by their low p-values and t-values above a certain threshold which indicate relatively larger differences (See Table 8).

Collaborative Practices	P-value	t	Difference
<i>Compliance to Laws and Circulars</i>	0.960	0.055	Not statistically significant.
<i>Recognition Program</i>	0.768	0.316	Not statistically significant.
<i>Technical Support</i>	0.495	0.750	Not statistically significant.
<i>Capacity Building</i>	0.831	0.228	Not statistically significant.
<i>Promotional Activities</i>	0.082	2.088	Statistically significant.
<i>Partnership and Linkages</i>	0.063	2.278	Statistically significant.

Legend: The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 8. Significant Difference of AHI between BOD and GM Groups

Discussion

Article XII, Section 1 of the 1987 Constitution outlines the national economic goals in the Philippines, which include achieving a more equitable distribution of opportunities, income, and wealth, sustaining increased production of goods and services for the people's benefit, and enhancing productivity to improve the quality of life, particularly for the underprivileged. To attain these goals, cooperatives are encouraged to expand their ownership base. Additionally, Section 15 of the same article highlights the significance of promoting the viability and growth of cooperatives as a means of achieving social justice and economic development. Consequently, Local Government Units (LGUs) play a pivotal role in cooperative development, contributing to both economic progress and the promotion of social justice among their members.

The Joint Memorandum Circular 2019-01 issued by DILG and CDA, where this study is based, outlines the roles of Local Government Units (LGUs) in the development of cooperatives in the Philippines. These roles encompass the formulation of Local Cooperative Development Plans in alignment with national and medium-term cooperative development plans, providing technical guidance, financial assistance, and support to enhance cooperatives as viable economic entities, promoting cooperative organization within their jurisdiction, appointing local cooperative officers, and establishing partnerships for sharing cooperative information and implementing development plans in collaboration with the Cooperative Development Authority (CDA), the primary government agency responsible for cooperative promotion, development, and regulation.

In this study, a survey was conducted, and the respondents expressed general Happiness with the collaborative practices and activities of the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Makati. This suggests that they are satisfied that the LGU complies with the mandates of the Cooperative Code of 2008 (RA 9520). Compliance with cooperative laws aligns with Republic Act 11535, signed into law by former President Rodrigo Duterte on April 9, 2021. This new law makes it mandatory for all local government units (LGUs) to appoint a Cooperatives Development Officer (CDO), amending the Local Government Code of 1991. The CDO is responsible for assisting groups and sectors in forming cooperatives and connecting regional cooperatives with relevant government agencies. Additionally, JMC 2019-01 requires LGUs to appoint a local cooperative officer to oversee cooperative development activities.

Similarly, respondents express Happiness with the LGU's Recognition Program, indicating the effective implementation of various recognition initiatives and events, including the *Koop Bida Awards*. This aligns with the LGUs' role in fostering cooperative organization and development within their jurisdiction, as outlined in JMC 2019-01, section 3.1.1.3. Furthermore, respondents also exhibit Happiness towards the LGU's Technical Support Activities. This implies their contentment with the Technical Assistance provided by the LGU, facilitated by the MCDO, including Compliance Forums, prompt responses to cooperative inquiries, valuable assistance in report generation, event coordination, and addressing troubleshooting issues related to mandated reports. Additionally, respondents demonstrate Happiness regarding the LGU's Capacity Building efforts. This indicates their satisfaction with the MCDO's role as the Cooperative Training Provider (CTPro) and their contentment with the LGU's efforts to cultivate a cadre of cooperative trainers actively engaged in delivering both mandated and non-mandated training. Respondents also express Happiness with MCDO's initiative to assist respondent cooperatives in formulating their Cooperative Business Continuity Program to enhance their preparedness for emergencies, disasters, and calamities, in accordance with JMC 2019-01, section 3.1.1.2, which emphasizes the LGUs' role in offering technical guidance, financial support, and other services to nurture cooperatives into viable and responsive economic entities. Furthermore, respondents are generally Happy with the LGU's Promotional Activities. This reflects their satisfaction with how the LGU promotes cooperatives as instruments of economic development and social justice, including events such as *Koop Kapatid*, *Ginoo at Ginang Kooperatiba*, *Koop Quiz Bee*, and the *Koop Caravan Program*, which promote cooperativism in Makati City at the barangay level. This aligns with the LGUs' role in encouraging cooperative organization and supporting their growth within their areas of jurisdiction, as prescribed in JMC 2019-01, section 3.1.1.3.

However, respondents express Moderate Happiness concerning the LGU's partnerships and linkages with organizations like CDCM, UPCM, FEMACO, and government agencies. This indicates the need for the Makati LGU to enhance efforts in facilitating collaboration among various entities, individuals, and communities to better harness resources, knowledge, and expertise for more effective pursuit of common objectives. Such collaboration allows the LGU and other organizations to leverage their strengths, expanding the impact of the cooperative movement in the city. Partnerships can open doors to new markets, customer bases, and distribution channels, fostering innovation and promoting peace, security, and economic cooperation. This aligns with the role of LGUs in establishing partnerships and cooperative development in tandem with the Cooperative Development Authority (CDA), the lead agency in cooperative promotion, development, and regulation.

To emulate Bhutan's approach of reducing poverty, protecting the environment, and fostering economic growth, cooperatives can enhance the well-being of their members by investing in education, healthcare, and essential services.

This involves modernizing education and providing digital financial literacy training. It also includes ensuring universal healthcare access, essential medicines, and healthcare facilities. Cooperatives can launch initiatives like the "Healthy Coop" campaign which can encourage healthy lifestyles. Moreover, focusing on mental and emotional well-being through practices like meditation, mindfulness, and yoga can reduce stress and promote positive mental health. Learning from Bhutan's success, leaders can create a prosperous, happy, and environmentally conscious cooperative for their members.

Thus, business organizations, like cooperatives, should prioritize happiness as their measure of primary economic growth, following the example set by Bhutan. The growth of a cooperative, measured by factors such as increased net surplus or dividends, would not necessarily equate to increased happiness among its members. While members might receive substantial dividends, their happiness may not necessarily follow suit. Conversely, members with lower dividends could still find genuine happiness in the cooperative's activities. Furthermore, there is a point at which the increase in economic growth no longer leads to a corresponding rise in happiness. Thus, to maximize the happiness of cooperative members, a wide range of factors and indicators must be taken into account, including economic growth, access to healthcare, educational opportunities, and overall quality of life. Through this approach, cooperative members can achieve the highest levels of happiness possible.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based from the findings of the study the following are recommended:

1. There is no statistical difference of the Average Happiness Index (AHI) between BOD and GM on Compliance to Laws and Circulars, Recognition Program, Technical Support, and Capacity Building all exhibited non-statistically significant differences which suggests that any disparities in these areas may be attributed to random variation. On the other hand, there exist a significant difference of the Average Happiness Index (AHI) between BOD and GM Promotional Activities and Partnership and Linkages.
2. Generally, the affiliates of the Federation of Makati are Happy of the Collaborative Practices and Activates of LGU Makati through the Makati Cooperative Development Office (MCDO). Compliance to Laws and Circulars have the highest AHI, followed by Recognition Programs, Technical Support, and Capacity Building, Promotional Activities, Partnership and Linkages got the lowest AHI.
3. Board of Directors and General Managers of Affiliates of FEMCO shares the same sentiments as evidenced by no significant difference t-test with regards to all Collaborative Practices and Activities except Promotional Activities, and Partnership and Linkages.
4. The LGU Makati should exert more effort in facilitating collaboration between different entities, organizations, individuals, or communities to maximize pooling of resources, knowledge, and expertise in order to achieve its common goals more effectively. By joining forces, LGU and cooperatives can leverage each other's strengths to achieve greater impact.
5. LGU and cooperatives should stablish partnerships with other Civil Society Organizations or even Non-Government Organizations, Environmental Groups, and even other secondary cooperatives and tertiary cooperatives in order to provide access to new markets, customer bases, or distribution channels and expand their reach. Collaborating with others can foster innovation and creativity by bringing together diverse perspectives, ideas, and experiences and consequently promote economic cooperation.
6. The LGU should create a unique collaborative program and activities to different types and sizes tailored to their respective needs. In this way, a more inclusive program can be implemented where the neediest cooperative can be fully visited with regards to its needs especially in the promotion of economic activity and cooperation.
7. There is an urgent need for private enterprises, including corporations, cooperatives, and similar collective organizations, need to move away from a money-centered model of economy to a happiness-based model, to not only broaden the base of their property ownership but also to spread happiness as an index of satisfaction to Projects, Programs, and Activities (PPAs) of any organization. While there may be an initial increase in happiness as a result of economic growth, beyond a certain point, this increase levels off and does not continue to rise with further economic growth. This means that in order to increase overall happiness, it is necessary to look beyond economic growth.
8. Cooperatives as a business organization should rethink and refocus their business objectives not on the economic side but on the general well-being of their members.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank officers of FEMACO for their participation, for the guidance, feedback, and support throughout the conduct of this research and the preparation of this manuscript. Any remaining errors or omissions are the sole responsibility of the author.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The author declare that has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in this research can be accessed through a formal request to the author of the study.

References

- Arns, V. D., & Lima, A. B. (2020). Implementation of the IHP—Internal Happiness Program of Cooperativism as a Management Tool. In *Operations Management for Social Good: 2018 POMS International Conference in Rio* (pp. 761-768). Springer International Publishing.
- Colston, P. (2023). The Finnish Secret to Happiness? Knowing When You Have Enough. *New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/04/01/world/europe/finland-happiness-optimism.html>
- Coop, A. & Routley, N. (2023). Mapped: The World's Happiest Countries in 2023. *Visual Capitalist*. <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/worlds-happiest-countries-2023/>
- Costanza, R., Hart, M., Posner, S., & Talberth, J. (2007). Beyond GDP: The Need for New Measures of Progress. *The Pardee Papers*, No.4. 2009.
- Cruz, BM. (2023, October 10). Quezon City is Philippines' richest city for third straight year. *Business World*. <https://www.bworldonline.com/the-nation/2023/10/10/550863/quezon-city-is-philippines-richest-city-for-third-straight-year/>
- Duque, J. P., & Dizon, J. T. (2018). Stakeholder Convergence in the Revitalization of Community-Based Enterprises: The Case of Halog West Producers' Cooperative in La Union, Philippines. *Journal of Economics, Management & Agricultural Development*, 4(2), 15-25.
- Gabriel, A., Sarmiento, R., & Viernez, M. (2021). Registered Cooperatives and Local Government Unit in the Province of Nueva Ecija Philippines: Status, Participation and the Way Forward. DOI:10.21203/rs.3.rs-531925/v1
- Garcia, P. (2023, October 30). Makati City chosen as sole city in PH, Asia Pacific Region as finalist in World Smart City Awards 2023. *Manila Bulletin*. <https://mb.com.ph/2023/10/30/makati-city-chosen-as-sole-city-in-ph-asia-pacific-region-as-finalist-in-world-smart-city-awards-2023>
- Hunter, M. (2023 March 20). The world's happiest countries for 2023. *CNN Travel*. Cable News Network. A Warner Bros. Discovery Company. <https://edition.cnn.com/travel/article/world-happiest-countries-2023-wellness/>
- Ilasco, I. (2021). Gross National Happiness: an alternative way to measure progress? *DevelopmentAid*. <https://www.developmentaid.org/news-stream/post/125464/gross-national-happiness-an-alternative-way-to-measure-progress>
- Launio, C. C., & Sotelo, M. C. B. (2021). "Concern for community": Case of cooperatives in the Cordillera Region, Philippines. *Journal of Co-operative Organization and Management*, 9(1), 100130.
- Makati City Basic Facts and Figures 2022. <https://www.makati.gov.ph/cms/content/facts-and-figures/632>
- Masterclass (2022). Economics 101: What Is the Difference Between GDP and GNP? <https://www.masterclass.com/articles/economics-101-what-is-the-difference-between-gdp-and-gnp>
- OECD. 2024. Bhutan's Gross National Happiness (GNH) Index. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/well-being-knowledge-exchange-platform-kep_93d45d63-en/

- Parrocha, A. (2021, April 14). New law makes coops dev't officer post mandatory in LGUs. Philippine News Agency (PNA). <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/>
- Republic Act No. 7854 (July 19, 1994). An Act Converting the Municipality of Makati into a Highly Urbanized City to be Known as the City of Makati. The Corpus Juris. Retrieved August 29, 2022.
- Russo, R. (2022). Bhutan is the Happiest Country in the World? Why is it #1? Optimal Happiness. <https://optimalhappiness.com/bhutan-happiest-country-in-the-world/>
- Seth, S. (2023, April 30). GDP vs. GNP: What's the Difference? Economics. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/030415/what-functional-difference-between-gdp-and-gnp.asp>
- Sunio, V., Gaspay, S. M., Rivera, J., Pontawe, J., Billones, R., Mora, R., ... & Darong, J. D. (2022). Development of Intelligent transportation system from the perspective of local government units, national government agencies and transportation cooperatives. *Innovatus: A Journal on Computing Technology Innovations*, 5(2), 1-6.
- Unacademy (2023). National Happiness Index. United Nation Academy. <https://unacademy.com/content/kerala-psc/study-material/kerala-population/national-happiness-index/>
- Ura, DK. (2021). Why Gross National Happiness matters more. *India Today*. <https://www.indiatoday.in/magazine/guest-column/story/20211004-why-gross-national-happiness-matters-more-1856623-2021-09-24>

Appendices

No appendices are included in this article.